

Business case

WP6 Y2Q4

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Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on the business cases for using the DECI service in Italy, Spain, Sweden, and Israel. Additionally, it provides a cross-case analysis and provides recommendations for future implementation of the service and further improving the business case.

The starting point for the business case is the approach set in D3.1, where the different potential DECI benefits were set out. This document focuses on quality of care, postponement of care, and quality of work. In order to structure the business case, a framework for developing business cases for long-term care was adopted from Dutch research organization TNO. The relevant KPI's in the DECI model were modelled by using data from the evaluation as conducted in WP5 and discussed in D6.1 and supplemented by insights from literature and inventories among the different partners.

For all sites, we ended up with a positive business case, purely looking at the monetary outcomes. The result of implementing the service in Italy was positive but small, while in Spain it was very high (a result of 1.152.016,71 euros in the third year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,74)). In Sweden the result was slightly above 0, just like in Israel. This very positive outcome for the case of Spain is due to their high patient number per clinical site, combined with the high costs in Spain for treating mild dementia. Additionally, healthcare professionals' costs were lowest in Spain. This is not due to the number of hours they invest here, but to the low tariffs that are being charged.

In order to improve the business case for the DECI solution we provide the following recommendations:

1. To look into the possibility of asking a monetary contribution from patients (however, one should treat with caution here, as willingness to pay was very low (as reported in D6.1));
2. To negotiate healthcare insurance compensation with insurers (as they are the main benefactors of the implementation of the service, but do not cover any costs);
3. To look into the possibility to offer the DECI solution as a software-only service by integrating commercial activity trackers (as the usage fee for the smartwatch soft- and hardware was high, while patient satisfaction with and acceptance of the technology was low, and they preferred using their own activity tracker).

Introduction

A business case is a description of value and cost of an innovation that could help decision-makers make informed decisions regarding future implementation of DECI. The description of a business case should highlight the advantages of the innovation explaining how DECI fulfilled the needs of patients and their caregivers, healthcare providers and society, in relation to the limited timeline of the intervention. Also, the business case should outline the discovered negatives.

The starting point of the business case analysis is the needs of patients, healthcare providers and society, outlined in the deliverable D1.3. The needs have been assessed against the technical and organizational capability and feasibility of different service providers in the DECI consortia. The outcomes were translated into the DECI business model, developed and described in the deliverables D2.2 and D3.1. In order to obtain insights on how DECI fulfils different needs when it is applied in real settings, the needs and features of the DECI business model have been reflected in the outcomes' evaluation perspectives and domains, as provided in the deliverable D6.1.

The business cases described in this document (D6.2) incorporate the results from all evaluation domains described in D6.1 per every pilot site, in combination with market data and insights derived from the scientific literature. The document finishes with a cross-case insights and a list of recommendations.

1 Methodological approach to business case design

1.1 From business modelling to business case design

Figure 1: From business model to business case

The Business Model adopted and developed in D3.1 provides a scalable, solid and general framework that identifies and assess the feasibility of key service packages to be delivered in DECI, which are useful for the phases associated to pilot design. Moreover, the framework offers insights about the potential impact of the various key service packages identified, in order to estimate the area of benefits that DECI project could impact. In particular, DECI Service Model and its service packages have the potential to impact various perspectives (i.e. clinical (patient, staff, informal caregiver), technological, safety, ethics, legal, social, process effectiveness and cost-effectiveness). The evaluation of outcomes that have been reached during 6 months intervention of every patient, and up to one year for the pilot organizations will provide preliminary suggestions about the outcomes that could be reached through the implementation of all the various service packages and about the aspects that will be monitored and assessed. A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was defined in the evaluation framework (D6.1) to assess different perspectives outlined in the Figure 1. In order to establish the boundaries and feasibility of the DECI innovation, the business case design will concern different elements from all the evaluation domains assessed and described in D6.1.

1.2 Methodological approach

The methodology used for determining the DECI business case is founded upon the business case development approach for Innovation in long term care by TNO (<http://www.businesscase-longtermcare.com/Introduction.aspx>). The premise of this approach is a comparison between a situation before and after introduction of a novel

healthcare technology, and on different fronts. This way, a multi-perspective view on the usefulness and economic value of the healthcare technology can be created. Figure 2 depicts the approach and the different evaluation domains.

Figure 2. Approach and evaluation domains of the TNO Business case model for innovation in long term care.

The first step in developing the business case is to determine which factors are of relevance for the topic of investigation and to determine ways in which to quantify them (if possible). The TNO model recognizes seven domains in which factors need to be determined, in order to create a full scope:

1. Spent time. The time spent by professionals while working with the technology
2. Quality of care. Consequences of using the technology on the quality of care (e.g., patient safety)
3. Prevent & postpone care. How does the implementation of the technology postpone or prevent the main healthcare issue or secondary issues?
4. Income. How is money generated?
5. Investment. How much investment is needed before the technology can be used
6. Operating expenses. Which costs are involved in using a technology after the initial investment?
7. Quality of work. How does the use of the technology affect the content of professional use or its context (e.g. job satisfaction)?

The next step is to gather data for each factor, if possible quantifiable. In the model this should be done for a before and after situation. Please note that within DECI, we will gather this data for the full intervention group (Group 2). Whenever possible, we will use data from the DECI evaluation. If a factor is not assessed in this evaluation, we will use scientific literature or estimates from the clinical partners.

1.3 Factors

Table 1 displays the different domains within the TNO model and the factors within each domain that we have identified for the DECI business case analysis.

Table 1. Business case domains, metrics, and sources.

	Metric	Source
Domain: Spent time		
Geriatrician time	Number of hours/tariff	D6.1
Nurse practitioner time	Number of hours/tariff	D6.1
Physiotherapist time	Number of hours/tariff	D6.1
Etcetera
Domain: Quality of care		
Clinical procedures	Number of team meetings involving clinical personnel, per patient	D6.1
	Average time spent in multidisciplinary team meetings	D6.1
	Number of participants per professional category involved in multidisciplinary team meetings	D6.1
	Average time spent for definition of treatment plans	D6.1
	Average time spent for the revision of treatment plans	D6.1
Patient satisfaction	High or low satisfaction	D6.1, Interviews
Quality of life	EQ-5D (human-related quality of life)	D6.1
Domain: Prevent & postpone care		

Postponement of cognitive impairment	Changes in MMSE	D6.1
	Long term effects (in cost-savings)	Literature
Prevention of falls	% of falls prevented	Literature
	Long term effects (in cost savings)	Literature
Domain: Income		
For hospitals: reimbursement	Annual reimbursement	Clinical partners inventory
For companies: Usage fees	Annual usage fee turnover	Technical partners inventory
For companies: Hardware sales	Annual hardware sales turnover	Technical partners inventory
Domain: Investment		
For hospitals: investment on the hospital side	One-time investment	Clinical partners inventory
For companies: investment on the company side	One-time investment for each additional clinical site	Technical partners inventory
Domain: Operating expenses		
Operating expenses for clinical sites	Annual operating expenses	Clinical partners inventory
Operating expenses for companies	Annual operating expenses per clinical site	Technical partners inventory
Domain: Quality of work		
Job satisfaction	High or low satisfaction	D6.1, Interviews

1.4 Data collection and analysis

In this Section, we will explain how we gathered the data points that were not derived from D6.1.

1.4.1 Postponement of cognitive impairment data

Postponement of cognitive impairment has been modelled on the basis of changes in MMSE over time in the full intervention group. Then, to assess the monetary consequences of this possible postponement, we have referred to annual costs associated with formal care for mild dementia (since mild cognitive impairment is a relatively new phenomenon and numbers for associated costs are not available). We have used the following numbers as the basis for our modelling (taken from Jönsson and Wimo, 2009):

- In Sweden, annual costs are 18.941 euros. Costs for MD treatment in Sweden were assumed to be equivalent to Italian MD treatment costs. The reason of not having MD treatment cost for Sweden is related to the use of a different diagnosis system. Since Italian and Spanish MD treatment costs were comparable, it was assumed appropriate to apply the Italian value for Sweden. The assumption has been approved by healthcare professionals from VGR.;
- In Italy, annual costs are 18.941 euros, a number which is the result of an internal calculation by the Italian clinical partner in DECI;
- In Spain, annual costs are 18.342 euros;
- In Israel, annual costs are 13.488 euros, modelled after costs in the UK, since an indication of costs for Israel is missing.

1.4.2 Prevention of falls data

The physical program within the DECI solution is based upon the OTAGO program. The OTAGO program is a physical intervention program, aimed to improve physical strength among older adults and to prevent falls. Therefore, prevention of falls, and the costs associated with falls have been modelled in the business case.

In order to model the consequences of following the physical training program in DECI, we have used the following parameters:

- People aged 65 and older fall, on average, 0.33 times per year (Gillespie et al., 2012);
- 9% of these falls lead to a GP visit (Berg et al., 1997);
- 5% of these falls lead to an ER visit (Berg et al., 1997);
- 3% of these falls lead to a fracture (project team estimation);
- Completing the OTAGO program prevents 68% of falls (Thomas et al., 2010).

1.4.3 Costs on the hospital side

An overview of costs on the hospital side (for providing the technology) was gathered by means of a survey among the clinical partners in the consortium, in which they were asked to provide a list of costs they made during the implementation and evaluation. Costs that were made for enabling the evaluation were removed from these overviews. Next, the overviews were discussed in plenary among clinical and technical partners, in order to get a complete and approved overview.

1.4.4 Costs on the company side

Like we did for gathering technical costs from the clinical sites, we also gathered an overview of technical costs from the technical partners via a survey. This focused on gathering usage fees, costs for hardware, etc. Next, the results were discussed in plenary among the technical partners in order to ensure completeness.

1.4.5 Business case analyses

Once all costs were gathered and inserted into a model, we calculated the following outcomes per implementation site:

- Monetary result of implementing the DECI service after year 1
- Monetary result of implementing the DECI service after year 2
- Monetary result of implementing the DECI service after year 3
- Benefits/costs ratio

These outcomes will define, together with outcomes that cannot be expressed in monetary value (e.g., patient satisfaction) whether or not implementing the DECI service is a worthwhile investment.

2 Results

In this section, we will discuss the results of the business case analysis per evaluation site. For each site, a forecast for three years has been made. After discussing each site in isolation, we will conduct a cross-case analysis in Section 2.5.

2.1 Italian business case results

For the Italian context, we have created an overview of the different benefits and costs, according to Table 1.

2.1.1 Spent time and Quality of care

Table 2 displays the costs associated with time spent by professionals. They are either specified as the time spent by each type of professional (for direct treatment), time spent during multi-disciplinary meetings (for which costs were calculated by the different types of professionals that were involved), and time spent for defining and revising care plans. Please note that the time spent for individual professionals on the one hand, and time spent in multi-disciplinary meetings and working on care plans on the other hand, does not overlap. For each year these costs will rise, due to an expected rise in patient numbers (100 for year 1, 150 for year 2, and 175 for year 3). In year 2, total costs will amount to 44.171,63 euros, and in year 3, will amount to 51.533,56 euros. Average costs per patient remain stable.

Table 2. Time spent in Italy, year 1.

Clinical costs				
<i>Professional</i>	<i>Hours [h]</i>	<i>Hourly tariff [€/h]</i>	<i>Total [€]</i>	<i>Total per patient [€/patient]</i>
Doctor	452,7	37	16.752,7	167,5
Nurse practitioner	44	18	792	7,92
Physiotherapist	88,8	24	2.133,3	21,3
Technician	0	21	0	0,00
Case manager	135,1	22,5	3.041,6	30,4
Psychologist	129,6	25	3.240,7	32,4
Multidisciplinary meeting	34,6		1.612,2	16,1
Definition & revision of care plans	75	25	1875	18,7
TOTALS	960,1		29.447,7	294,4

2.1.2 Patient satisfaction

Half of the Italian patients stressed that the simplicity of the physical training system was an advantage for participants' understanding and motivation. Furthermore, a majority of participants thought that the exercises were not challenging enough for them. One patient reported that it would have been useful to have some kind of interaction with clinicians when performing the different activities.

Most interviewees in the Italian pilot thought that cognitive games have been challenging and stimulating, especially in relation to the fact that the games were able to provide a personal development over time. However, a quarter of the patients, using the cognitive game program, considered the navigation in the system to be difficult, especially one participant could not use the system without an informal caregiver being present to aid and support.

All Italian interviewed patients using the watch argue that they got used wearing it. However, all patients reported that they did not like the size of the watch. Previous ICT experience was a facilitator to use the tablet. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service. Even though the navigation of the DECI system worked well for many patients, help was needed from a daughter, grandson or husband, to get started with the DECI system in a few cases. A greater part of the Italian interviewees emphasized that they would use DECI-system in the future as an aid to keep active both physically and cognitively.

2.1.3 Quality of life

Quality of Life was measured using a standardized instrument EuroQL-5D-5L. The analysis for Group 2 patients showed that there was not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in any of EQ-5D-5L dimensions between baseline and follow-up phases. From a purely descriptive point of view, after 6 months Group 2 reported the proportion of people reporting 'no problem' in every dimension changed in the following way: Mobility – increased 14,28%; Self-care – decreased 4,76%; Usual activity – increased 9,52%; Pain/discomfort – decreased 4,76%; Anxiety/depression – increased 4,76%. However, the result was not statistically significant. No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and after 6 months. From the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 decreased 13,5% indicating worse 'health today' after 6 months. This result is not statistically significant.

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D index values between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 decreased 3,21%. The result is not statistically significant.

2.1.4 Prevent & postpone care

Table 3 displays how much costs were prevented in year 1 by implementing the DECI solution with respect to care that has been postponed (Mild dementia costs) and care that has been prevented (care as a consequence of falls). In year 2 and 3 these costs rise (total costs are, respectively 237.682,74 euros and 277.296,53 euros), due to the rising number of patients that work with the DECI solution.

Table 3. Italian care costs prevented and postponed due to the implementation of DECI (year 1).

Prevention & postponement of care		After 12 months	Costs [€]	Total costs prevented [€]
<i>Mild dementia</i>				
% of instances of MD postponed		8%		151.528,00
<i>Falls</i>				
% of falls prevented		68%		
Number of falls prevented		68		
Number of GP consults prevented		6,12	15	91,80
Number of emergency room visits prevented		3,4	241	819,40
Number of fractures prevented		2,04	2.949	6.015,96
			TOTAL	158.455,16

2.1.5 Income

From a hospital or societal point of view, income (as seen in monetary units) will be 0, as the Italian healthcare system does not allow for reimbursement for this kind of care from care insurance. Nor is it foreseen that patients pay for the service by themselves.

2.1.6 Investment

For the Italian context, investment expenses, made by the hospital, are relatively small. They amount to 140 euros in personnel costs for establishing the ICT infrastructure (mostly done by the technology providers) and 660 euros in personnel for configuring tablets.

2.1.7 Operating expenses

Table 4 and 5 display the operating expenses for the Italian context. These costs occur annually and can be divided into usage fees for the different DECI ICT modules, and operating costs for locally hosting the technology. In year 2 and 3, these costs rise due to the inclusion of more patients. Table 4 shows that the smartwatch usage fee is relatively high. This is because the Integrated platform and Coaching and training system usage fees only include software, while the smartwatch usage fee also includes the lease of hardware. Main cost post among the annual technology costs that become the hospital is the purchase of tablets for the patients.

Table 4. Annual usage fees for the DECI service in Italy, year 1.

Usage fees		
<i>Service provider</i>		Including Tax
Integrated platform usage fee	9.000	9.000
Coaching and training system usage fee	5.000	5.000
Smartwatch usage fee	30.000	36.600
Integration fee	1.500	1.500
Total usage fee	45.500	52.100

Table 5. Annual Italian technology costs involved in implementing the DECI service, year 1.

Technology costs - Operating expenses (annually)		Euro
<i>Service provider</i>		
<i>Hospital</i>		
Server for hosting		1.830
Cost for configuring tablets		660
Maintenance personnel		110
ePersonam platform		15.243
Teamviewer license		955
1st line helpdesk		10.800
4G connectivity for patients		7.900
Tablets for patients and operators (depreciation 12 months)		35.000
4 computers for the control room (depreciation 12 months)		2.148
	TOTAL FOR HOSPITAL	74.646

2.1.8 Quality of work

Healthcare professionals in Italy have reported spending on average 29,3 hours per week working in the DECI care model, and all the professionals indicated that their workload increased. The reason of the workload increase was identified as data entering into the

DECI platform for the purposes of the study. However, all the respondents stressed that they could meet their work demands and personal standards of work quality. The benefits manifested in a form of a larger empowerment of professionals being able to provide patients useful tools and enrich care provided. Also, it has widened professionals' knowledge about cognitive impairment and helped to better understand patients' needs and status. Also, the data was easier to share between the professionals.

2.1.9 Italian business case outcome

The result of implementing the DECI service in the Italian context has a positive monetary result of 1.461,41 euros in the first year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,01), a positive result of 38.315,11 euros in the second year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,19), and a positive result of 56.741,97 euros in the third year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,26).

2.2 Spanish business case results

The discussion of the results for the Spanish business case will follow the same structure as we used for discussing the Italian business case.

2.2.1 Spent time and quality of care

Table 6 displays the costs that were made on personnel costs for care professionals in year 1. It shows the inclusion of nurses, neuropsychologists, and geriatricians. We also calculated costs for defining and revising care plans (no overlap with individual professionals' hours). In the first year, these costs amount to 221.151 euros, in the second year they amount to 331.726,50 euros, and in the third year they amount to 387.014,25 euros. This rise is due to the anticipated rise in patient numbers: 1.000 in year 1, 1.500 in year 2, and 1750 in year 3.

Table 6. Spent time in year 1 in Spain.

Clinical costs				
<i>Professional</i>	<i>Hours [h]</i>	<i>Hourly tariff [€/h]</i>	<i>Total [€]</i>	<i>Total per patient [€/patient]</i>
Nurse	1.500	13,37	20.055	20,06
Neuropsychologist	4.000	21,28	85.120	85,12
Geriatrician	2.650	21,28	56.392	56,39
Definition & revision of care plans	2.800	21,28	59.584	59,58
TOTALS			221.151	221,15

2.2.2 Patient satisfaction

No patients gave an opinion on the physical exercise system. Interview data from one Spanish patient indicated that the DECI-system was too immature to be used for that specific patient. No patients from Spain gave any opinions on the watch. None of the Spanish participants reported a willingness to use of the DECI-system in the future. No patients provided information on the tablet or integrated care platform.

2.2.3 Quality of life

Quality of Life was measured using a standardized instrument EuroQL-5D-5L. The sample of patients was very small and consisted of 7 people. The analysis for Group 2 patients showed that there was not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in any of EQ-5D-5L dimensions between baseline and follow-up phases. From a purely descriptive point of view, after 6 months Group 2 reported the proportion of people reporting 'no problem' in every dimension changed in the following way: Mobility – decreased 50%; Self-care – no change; Usual activity – no change; Pain/discomfort – no change; Anxiety/depression – increased 50%. However, the result was not statistically significant.

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 decreased 9,09% indicating worse 'health today' after 6 months. The result is not statistically significant. No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D index values between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 decreased 1,30%. The result is not statistically significant.

2.2.4 Prevent & postpone care

Table 7 shows much must costs were prevented (in terms of falls and subsequent costs) and postponed (by postponing mild dementia). In year 1, these costs amount to 1.552.020 euros, in year 2 to 2.328.030 euros, and in year 3 to 2.716.035 euros. These numbers rise because of the rise in patient population.

Table 7. Cost prevented or postponed, due to the implementation of DECI in Spain, year 1.

Prevention & postponement of care	After 12 months	Costs [€]	Total costs prevented [€]
<i>MD</i>			
% of instances of MD postponed	8%		1.467.360,00
<i>Falls</i>			
% of falls prevented	68%		
Number of falls prevented	680		
Number of GP consults prevented	61,2	39	2.386,80
Number of emergency room visits prevented	34	518	17.612,00
Number of fractures prevented	20,4	3.170	64.661,20
		TOTAL	1.552.020,00

2.2.5 Income

In Spain, reimbursement of the costs made because of the implementation of the DECI service are not possible. Therefore, income was set to 0.

2.2.6 Investment

The investment on the hospital side was 0 in Spain, as the site could work with installation by the technology suppliers via distance (and whose installation costs are processed into the usage fees).

2.2.7 Operating expenses

Table 8 displays the usage fees for the different software services in Spain, for year 1. In year 2, these costs amount to 560.000 euros (including taxes), and in year 3 to 650.750 euros (including taxes). This rise is due to the rising fee for the smartwatch, which is dependent on the number of patients.

Table 8. Usage fees in Spain, year 1.

Usage fees		
<i>Service provider</i>		Including taxes
Integrated platform usage fee	9.000	9.000
Coaching and trainign system usage fee	5.000	5.000
Smartwatch usage fee	300.000	363.000
Integration fee	1.500	1.500
Total usage fee	315.500	378.500

Table 9 displays the operating expenses for the use of the DECI services, as are to be paid by the hospital. In year 1, they amount to 451.254 euros, in year 2 to 501.254 euros, and in year 3 to 526.254 euros. This rise is due to the increase in helpdesk costs, related to the increase in the number of patients.

Table 9. Spanish operating expenses, year 1.

Technology costs - Operating expenses (annually)	Euro
<i>Hospital</i>	
Hosting server	1.244
Domain	10
Tablets (depreciation time 12 months)	350.000
1st line helpdesk	100.000
Total	451.254

2.2.8 Quality of work

Healthcare professionals in Spain have reported spending on average 4,3 hours per week working in the DECI care model, and all the professionals indicated that their workload increased. The reason of the workload increase was related to managing patients' participation (willingness to participate) in the DECI study. However, all the respondents stressed that they could meet their work demands and personal standards of work quality. The benefits manifested in a form of a quicker and facilitated contact with patients and caregivers. Also, the time saved for physical visits, since recommendations could be given remotely, which had a positive effect on the work.

2.2.9 Spanish business case outcome

The result of implementing the DECI service in the Spanish context has a monetary result of 501.114,96 euros in the first year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,48), a result of 935.049,46 euros in the second year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,67), and a result of 1.152.016,17 euros in the third year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,74).

2.3 Swedish business case results

The discussion of the results of the business case analysis will follow the same structure as in Sections 2.1 and 2.2.

2.3.1 Spent time and quality of care

Table 10 displays the Swedish costs for the care professionals that were involved in providing the DECI service, for year 1. For year 2 and 3, these costs are respectively 620.161,79 euros and 723.522,09 euros, due to a higher number of patients that utilize the intervention (500 patients are expected to use the service in year 1, 750 patients in year 2, and 875 patients in year 3).

Table 10. Spent time and quality of care (expressed in multidisciplinary meetings) in Sweden, year 1.

Clinical costs				
	<i>Hours [h]</i>	<i>Hourly tariff [€/h]</i>	<i>Total [€]</i>	<i>Total per patient [€/patient]</i>
Geriatrician	1.500,00	84,00	126.000,00	252,00
Nurse practitioner	2.452,38	34,00	83.380,95	166,76
Physician	1.202,38	61,00	73.345,24	146,69
Assistant Nurse	250,00	26,00	6.500,00	13,00
Multidisciplinary meeting	37,80		19.215,00	38,43
Definition & revision of care plans	1.250,00	84,00	105.000,00	210,00
Total			413.441,20	826,88

2.3.2 Patient satisfaction

Most of the patients have appreciated the possibility to use IT-assisted physical exercise programs that can be performed in a home environment. In many cases, patients declared that they would like to continue using this program after the finished interventions. Perceived drawbacks were reported by a few, mainly in relation to instructions for specific exercises.

A majority of the Swedish patients valued the variation and the amusement aspects of the cognitive games, stimulating them to use the system and to challenge themselves. More than half of the Swedish participants repeatedly experienced Login problems, lasting both for shorter and longer periods. Patients reported that they got tired of not being able to login to the system. Translations were perceived as incorrect and software design could have been more intuitive.

Swedish patients believed that the watch was not visually appealing, due to its design and size. Interviews also indicated that patients were interested in monitoring their own

pedometer data, and that they are used to getting it from other devices. Previous ICT experience was a facilitator to use the tablet. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service. Most Swedish patients seemed to have managed to navigate in the DECI system with support from professionals. One participant reports that guidance from his wife was needed in the beginning. Most patients in the Swedish intervention highlighted that physical exercises would be something they are willing to also use after the project ends. One might also argue that the compliance to a program recommended by professionals or in a prescription can be higher, compared to programs on the internet without a recommendation from a professional.

2.3.3 Quality of life

Quality of Life was measured using a standardized instrument EuroQL-5D-5L. The analysis for Group 2 patients showed that there was not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in any of EQ-5D-5L dimensions between baseline and follow-up phases. From a purely descriptive point of view, Group 2 reported worse or unchanged results after 6 months of intervention, in comparison to the baseline. After 6 months, the proportion of people reporting 'no problem' in every dimension changed in the following way: Mobility – decreased 5,26%; Self-care – no change; Usual activity – decreased 5,26%; Pain/discomfort – decreased 5,26%; Anxiety/depression – no change. However, the result was not statistically significant. No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 increased 7,86% indicating better 'health today' after 6 months. However, the result is not statistically significant. No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D index values between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 increased 2,03%. However, the result is not statistically significant.

2.3.4 Prevent & postpone care

Table 11 shows how much costs were prevented by implementing the DECI solution in the Swedish context (focused on preventing mild dementia and preventing falls). In year 1, costs that are saved in this way amount to 776.290,19 euros. In year 2, they rise to 1.164.435,29 euros, and in year 3 to 1.358.507,83 euros, due to the rising number of patients that make use of the intervention.

Table 11. Prevented & postponed care in Sweden, year 1

Prevention & postponement of care			
	After 12 months	Costs [€]	Total costs prevented [€]
<i>MD</i>			
% of instances of MD postponed	8%		757.640,00
<i>Falls</i>			
% of falls prevented	68%		
Number of falls prevented	340		
Number of GP consults prevented	30,6	179,45	5.491,17
Number of emergency room visits prevented	17	448,14	7.618,38
Number of fractures prevented	10,2	543,2	5.540,64
		TOTAL	776.290,19

2.3.5 Income

As was the case for Italy and Spain, eHealth interventions such as the DECI service are not eligible for reimbursement by care insurance. Therefore, income was set to 0.

2.3.6 Investment

In Sweden, an initial investment per clinical site needs to be made consisting of personnel for local installation (4.365 euros) and purchase of tablets for training purposes (55 pieces, total cost 14.271 euros). This amounts to a total investment of 18.636 euros.

2.3.7 Operating expenses

Table 12 displays the usage fees for using the DECI service in Sweden. These costs are constant, except for the smartwatch usage fee, which increases with patient size (in year 2 and 3). In year 1, usage fees amount to 203.000 euros, in year 2 to 296.750, and in year 3 to 343.625 euros.

Table 12. Usage fees for the DECI service in Sweden, year 1.

Usage fees		
<i>Service provider</i>		Including tax
Integrated platform usage fee	9.000	9.000
Coaching and trainign system usage fee	5.000	5.000
Smartwatch usage fee	150.000	187.500
Integration fee	1.500	1.500
Total usage fee	165.500	203.000

Table 13 displays the annual operating expenses for the clinical site, when implementing the DECI service. While costs for hosting, maintenance and management are constant, the

costs for the helpdesk increase each year, due to a rise in patient numbers (and thus, calls to the helpdesk). The total number of operating expenses amounts to 145.015 euros in year 1, 203.215 euros in year 2, and 232.315 euros in year 3.

Table 13. Annual operating expenses in Sweden, year 1.

Technology costs - Operating expenses (annually)	SEK	Euro
<i>Hospital</i>		
Server for hosting	75.000	7.275
Personnel for maintenance	30.000	2.910
1st line helpdesk	1.200.000	116.400
Management	190.000	18.430
	Total	145.015

2.3.8 Quality of work

Healthcare professionals in Sweden have reported spending on average 29,3 hours per week working in the DECI care model, and all the professionals indicated that their workload increased. The reason of the workload increase was related to the unique care model applied in Sweden employing a mobile team to conduct patient home visits. Although an overtime has been reported, it was mostly related due to the set-up of the study and data entry for the research purposes. However, all the respondents stressed that they could meet their work demands and personal standards of work quality. The benefits manifested in a form of a better overview of the overall patient situation, mainly due to observations at patient's home environment or being a case manager.

2.3.9 Swedish business case outcome

The result of implementing the DECI service in the Swedish context has a negative monetary result of 3.802,13 euros in the first year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,00), a result of 44.308,49 euros in the second year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,04), and a result of 59.045,74 euros in the third year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,05).

2.4 Israeli pilot site

The discussion of the Israeli business case discussion follows the same structure as the three previous business case analyses.

2.4.1 Spent time and quality of care

Table 14 displays the Israeli costs that were incurred in offering the DECI service in terms of care professionals' hours. Like Spain, in the Israeli context there are no multi-disciplinary meetings. In year 1, these costs amount to 38.000,00 euros, in year 2 to 57.000,00 euros, and in year 3 to 66.500,00 euros. This rise is due to the rising number of patients that were estimated for an Israeli clinical site (100 for year 1, 150 for year 2, and 175 for year 3).

Table 14. Spent time in year 1 in Israel.

Clinical costs				
	<i>Hours [h]</i>	<i>Hourly tariff [€/h]</i>	<i>Total [€]</i>	<i>Total per patient [€/patient]</i>
<i>Professional</i>				
Doctor	759,38	40,00	30.375,00	303,75
Nurse	96,88	18,00	1.743,75	17,44
Technician	50,00	21,00	1.050,00	10,50
Physiotherapist	109,38	35,00	3.828,13	38,28
Social worker	6,25	18,00	112,50	1,13
Occupational therapist	15,63	25,00	390,63	3,91
Definition & revision of care plans	20,00	25,00	500,00	5,00
Totals			38.000,00	380,00

2.4.2 Patient satisfaction

Most patients reported an appreciation of physical exercises that was prescribed by the healthcare professionals. However, a majority of patients also implied that the recommended exercises did not match their physical status. "The level was very low, and the movies were very slow. I did not have patience for that". Another participant argued that there is no obvious connection between the physical training and memory. Another patient did not feel confident when using the system, due to many software problems in the exercise program.

Cognitive games were appreciated by participants, mainly because the games were diversified for different needs. Even though most patients argued that the exercises were

not challenging enough. Other patients considered the system as challenging to handle practically. Translation issues and software design were the most reported problems. Israeli patients reported that they got used to wearing the watch, however, the purpose of using the watch was not clear to them.

Previous ICT experience was a facilitator to use the tablet. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service. Most patients could use the DECI system independently. However, some patients needed help from relatives to use the system. Israeli patients are ambivalent towards a future use of the DECI-system. Approximately half of the patients would like to go on using the DECI-technology. There is a clear connection between patients that were able to manage the system by themselves and the future use of the DECI-system. In other words, if one can use the system without help, the chance that the system will be used increases.

2.4.3 Quality of life

Quality of Life was measured using a standardized instrument EuroQL-5D-5L. The sample of patients was very small and consisted of 13 people. The analysis for Group 2 patients showed that there was not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in any of EQ-5D-5L dimensions between baseline and follow-up phases. From a purely descriptive point of view, after 6 months Group 2 reported the proportion of people reporting 'no problem' in every dimension changed in the following way: Mobility – decreased 25%; Self-care – no change; Usual activity – increased 12,5%; Pain/discomfort – decreased 12,5%; Anxiety/depression – increased 37,50%. However, the result was not statistically significant. No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 decreased 1,71% indicating worse 'health today' after 6 months. However, the result is not statistically significant. No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D index values between baseline and after 6 months. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores in Group 2 increased 0,24%. However, the result is not statistically significant.

2.4.4 Prevent & postpone care

Table 15 shows how much care costs could either be prevented or postponed by introducing the DECI service, for year 1. They are focused on postponement of care related to mild dementia and care related to falls. In year 2, these costs are expected to rise, due to the growing patient population and will amount to 178.828,80 euros (year 2) and 208.633,60 (year 3).

Table 15. Cost prevented or postponed, due to the implementation of DECI in Israel, year 1.

Prevention & postponement of care			
	After 12 months	Costs [€]	Total costs [€]
<i>Cognitive decline</i>			
% of instances of MD postponed	8%		107.904,00
<i>Falls</i>			
% of falls prevented	68%		
Number of falls prevented	68		
Number of GP consults prevented	6,12	60,00	367,20
Number of emergency room visits prevented	3,4	220,00	748,00
Number of broken hips prevented	2,04	5.000,00	10.200,00
		Total	119.219,20

2.4.5 Income

As for the previous sites, we inventoried whether or not the costs associated with implementing the DECI solution could be reimbursed via healthcare insurance. Like for the previous sites, this was not the case in Israel and the number for Income was therefore set to 0.

2.4.6 Investment

The investment for installing the DECI service on the hospital side was relatively small. Only the involvement of some ICT personnel was needed for installing the technology locally. Costs amounted to 1.000 euros.

2.4.7 Operating expenses

The operating expenses for using the DECI service in Israel can be split into usage fees (Table 16) and annual costs which were made at the Israeli clinical site (Table 17). The usage fees in Israel amounted to 50.600 euros for year 1. In year 2 and 3, all usage fees were constant, except for the smartwatch usage fee, which increased along with the number of patients. Therefore, total usage fees for year 2 amounted to 68.150 euros, and for year 3 they amounted to 76.925 euros.

Table 16. Usage fees for the DECI service in Israel, year 1.

Usage fees		
<i>Service provider</i>		Including tax
Integrated platform usage fee	9.000,00	9.000,00
Coaching and training system usage fee	5.000,00	5.000,00
Smartwatch usage fee	30.000,00	35.100,00
Integration fee	1.500,00	1.500,00
Total usage fee	45.500,00	50.600,00

The operating expenses in year 1 amounted to 21.540 euros. Server costs and maintenance personnel costs remained constant, but helpdesk costs are expected to rise, due to an increase of patients. Therefore, the total number of Israeli operating expenses are 23.640 euros in year 2, and 24.690 euros in year 3.

Table 17. Operating expenses in Israel, year 1.

Technology costs - Operating expenses (annually)	
<i>Hospital</i>	
Server costs	5.340,00
Personnel	12.000,00
Helpdesk	4.200,00
Total	21.540,00

2.4.8 Quality of work

Healthcare professionals in Israel have reported spending on average 1,5 hours per week working in the DECI care model, and all the professionals indicated that their workload increased. The reason of the workload increase was related to managing patients' participation (willingness to participate) in the DECI research. However, all the respondents stressed that they could meet their work demands and personal standards of work quality. The benefits manifested in a form of a larger empowerment of professionals being able to provide patients useful tools and enrich care provided. Also, it has widened professionals' knowledge about cognitive impairment and helped to better understand patients' needs and status.

2.4.9 Israeli business case outcome

The result of implementing the DECI service in the Israeli context has a positive monetary result of 8.079,20 euros in the first year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,072), a result of 30.038,80 euros in the second year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,20), and a result of 40.518,60 euros in the third year (benefits/costs ratio of 1,24).

2.5 Cross-case analysis

In Italy, the business case is positive after the first year itself, mainly due to averagely high hourly rates of different professionals compared to other countries, and lower local IT infrastructure-related costs. Also, the potential annual patient population is estimated to be 100 patients, which does not dramatically affect the cost related to purchasing the tablets. In Sweden, multi-disciplinary teams are an important part of the DECI model. This is reflected in their business case, with very high numbers for professionals' involvement per patient (826,88 euros per patient, compared to 236,03 euros per patient in Spain, where hourly tariffs are also far lower). The combination of many professionals' hours of work, combined with high tariffs make it difficult to create a positive monetary business case, even though in Sweden patients are expected to bring their own tablet (unlike at the other three sites), and thus, a huge costs post is not present in the Swedish business case. In Spain, the business case result is positive after the first year itself, due to a high estimated potential annual patient population and lower personnel cost. Also, the technology-related costs were relatively low.

In Israel, the business case has a neutral monetary result, due to high hourly tariffs of personnel and relatively smaller potential savings on prevented MD treatment.

Patient satisfaction was positive in all sites (except for Spain, where patient satisfaction could not be assessed), with the remark that the DECI technology needs to mature further (all sites), or that patients prefer to use their own activity sensor, instead of the smartwatch technology (voiced in Sweden and Israel). With respect to Quality of Life, there were no effects of introducing the DECI technology in any of the sites. Professionals in all countries perceived DECI as providing benefits to their job, such as widened knowledge about cognitive impairment, obtained more tools facilitating work with patients, and better understanding of their needs and status. All the respondents believed that due to DECI they can keep the current or increase their job performance in relation to patients. However, the workload issues have been reported in three countries (Italy, Israel, Sweden).

In all, implementing the DECI solution will not result in a huge saving of money (except for the Italian and Spanish contexts), nor will it cost money. Furthermore, quality of life will not be affected. On the other hand, illness is prevented at no extra costs (which means a decreased burden for older adults), patient satisfaction rises, and care professionals gain skills (to the cost of an increased workload).

Furthermore, the business cases described in this document could provide insights when aiming to exploit the DECI business model in different settings (e.g. in D6.3 we reported an example of application in the Netherlands and Lombardy Region).

3 Recommendations and Conclusions

In Section 2, we presented the business cases of implementing the DECI solution for Italy, Spain, Sweden and Israel, and provided a cross case analysis which showed that implementing the solution only results in large monetary benefits in Spain, while for the other three sites, the monetary result of introducing the service was neutral. On the other hand, illness was prevented, patient satisfaction rises, and care professionals gain skills.

It is possible to improve the business case further by means of several changes in the service model or the payment structure.

1. **Patient contribution.** In the current business cases, income for the hospital was set to 0, as reimbursement from healthcare insurance is no option. To divide the costs over hospitals and patients, one could opt to ask a small monthly usage fee from patients as well. However, this is a somewhat risky approach, as willingness-to-pay analysis (see D6.1) showed that most of the users were not willing to pay for the DECI solution, even though they demonstrated the positive outlook and willingness to use. Asking them to pay along could therefore result in low technology adoption.
2. **Healthcare insurance contribution.** In the same vein as the recommendation above, the financial burden on the hospital could be alleviated by incorporating insurance reimbursement. Due to a lack of regulation in the different sites, this would mean that negotiations will have to be started with insurers. However, since the benefit in terms of money befalls the insurers, this is certainly a negotiation with potential (especially in the Spanish context).
3. **Offer the DECI solution as a software-only service.** Currently, usage costs for the smartwatch technology take up the biggest part of the usage fees. Meanwhile, patients were dissatisfied with the design and perceived usefulness of the watch in two of the four trial sites and preferred to use their own activity tracker. Therefore, in order to decrease costs and to improve patient satisfaction, it should be explored whether or not the smartwatch technology can be replaced by the use of a different activity tracker (e.g. Fitbit). Then, a clinical site can choose to use smartwatch (and accept the usage fees), or to ask patients to use their own activity tracker or to purchase one (thereby lowering usage fees).

With respect to the calculation of the business case itself, it would be worthwhile to improve its quality by collecting additional data and incorporating it in the calculations. For example, we did not have numbers that indicated how much informal care would cost for patients with mild dementia. Therefore, we could only elaborate the direct healthcare costs. Incorporating informal care costs would further strengthen the business case, **costs that varies substantially between different countries, due to different views on informal care.**

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